

Using Smart Complexes To Optimize The Pace Of Students' Vocational Training

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Abstract. The use of SMART complexes with artificial intelligence elements in vocational education institutions in Ukraine enhances the quality and flexibility of learning, addressing challenges posed by wartime conditions and facilitating the transition to Vocational Education 4.0. This study investigates the effectiveness of SMART complexes in optimizing the pace of vocational training by comparing remote education in the central-eastern region, often disrupted by air-raid alerts and power outages, with in-person learning in the western region. Surveys of students and instructors, along with an analysis of learning outcomes, reveal the advantages of individualized learning enabled by artificial intelligence technologies.

The research employs a mixed-methods approach, integrating qualitative and quantitative data to evaluate the impact of different learning models on student performance. Findings indicate that SMART complexes promote personalized learning, enabling students to progress at their own pace while adjusting task complexity according to their abilities. In the central-eastern region, remote education is essential for maintaining educational continuity, whereas the fixed pace of in-person learning in the western region limits adaptability.

The study concludes that SMART complexes significantly enhance vocational education by fostering personalized approaches, developing digital skills, and increasing motivation. Their integration ensures effective adaptation of educational content to individual needs and labor market demands, offering a robust solution for optimizing the educational process under contemporary conditions.

Keywords: Vocational Training 4.0, SMART Complex, Artificial Intelligence.

1 Problem Statement

The use of SMART complexes with artificial intelligence (AI) elements in the professional training of students in vocational education institutions in Ukraine is a crucial step toward improving the quality of educational process organization [1]. This is particularly relevant in the context of martial law, where educational institutions face new challenges such as the forced transition to distance learning, reduced availability of resources for

practical training, and the need to ensure an individualized approach for students in diverse socio-economic and psychological conditions [2].

A SMART complex for an academic discipline is an interconnected set of regulatory and instructional-methodological materials that exist within the educational institution's information and learning environment and are necessary for the effective development of competencies as a programmed learning outcome of the discipline [3]. Professional training 4.0 involves the use of digital technologies to create a more interactive, personalized, and efficient learning environment. SMART complexes equipped with artificial intelligence elements have significant potential to support this transition. The integration of SMART complexes into the educational process opens new perspectives, allowing adaptation to modern conditions and facilitating the transition to the concept of Professional Training 4.0 [4].

These complexes are particularly important in situations where vocational education must rapidly respond to changes in the labor market. Changes driven by war, European integration processes, and global techno-technological trends impose new requirements on the training of qualified specialists [5]. The use of SMART complexes in the educational process aligns with Ukraine's digital transformation strategy in education, which is being implemented as part of the European educational space [6]. This approach ensures the integration of international standards into Ukrainian vocational education, enhancing its competitiveness and quality.

2 Analysis of Recent Research Works and Publications

SMART education is a process of acquiring and enhancing knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits through various forms of cognitive activity based on the integration of digital technologies and innovative methodologies. The acronym SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound) emphasizes the goal of SMART education – to create an effective and adaptive learning experience [7]. One of the key characteristics of SMART education is its reliance on advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) [8], augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR) [9], and the Internet of Things (IoT) [10].

Artificial intelligence plays a crucial role in optimizing the learning process within SMART complexes by adapting content to students' proficiency levels. The primary AI algorithms used in SMART complexes include machine learning (ML) for prediction and classification, deep learning for recognizing complex patterns, adaptive testing to adjust task difficulty based on performance, and evolutionary algorithms for finding optimal solutions [11]. Additionally, optimization algorithms enhance processes and planning, while natural language processing (NLP) technologies enable effective user interaction through text or voice. These algorithms collectively create adaptive and efficient systems that ensure a high level of personalization and accuracy in learning [12]. By fostering engaging and interactive environments, these technologies cater to diverse learning styles and paces. The implementation of personalized learning platforms enables automatic progress analysis, offering customized content that considers individual strengths and weaknesses, thus improving the overall learning experience [13].

Another key aspect of SMART education is its data-driven approach. Educational platforms collect and analyze student performance data, providing educators with valuable insights for refining curricula and teaching strategies. Furthermore, SMART education prioritizes inclusivity, making education accessible to all learners, including students with disabilities and those from remote areas, through digital resources and innovative technologies [14].

By fostering critical thinking, problem-solving, and digital literacy skills, SMART education promotes lifelong learning and adaptability [15]. It expands access to quality education through professional training tools that simulate real-world scenarios [16].

One of the most significant advantages of using SMART complexes in vocational education is their adaptability. For example, adaptive learning algorithms assess individual student performance and adjust task difficulty accordingly. This level of personalization not only enhances the educational process but also ensures more effective professional readiness among students [17]. Another key feature of SMART complexes is their ability to integrate theoretical knowledge with practical application. Simulated environments, virtual laboratories, and industry-based projects allow students to practice skills in contexts closely resembling real-world scenarios [18]. The organization of the educational process using SMART complexes facilitates the optimization of learning pace through data-driven analytics. By focusing on continuous improvement, SMART complexes help maintain a stable and productive learning trajectory [19].

3 Statement of Basic Material and the Substantiation of the Obtained Results

The study employs a mixed-methods approach that integrates both quantitative and qualitative methods. Specifically, a survey was conducted among 16,792 students [20] and 4,600 educators [21] to assess the effectiveness of implementing SMART complexes in vocational education. The survey remains open, and data collection will continue until June 1, 2025. Statistical analysis of the collected data enabled the evaluation of the impact of digital technologies on students' academic performance across various regions of Ukraine. For qualitative analysis, interviews with teachers were conducted to highlight regional specifics of SMART complex implementation, along with observations of the educational process to assess changes in the learning pace. A comparative analysis was carried out on the outcomes of distance, blended, and face-to-face learning, taking into account regional conditions and the influence of martial law. The system analysis method facilitated a comprehensive assessment of the interaction between technological, organizational, and pedagogical factors in the implementation of innovative teaching methods. The use of content analysis allowed for the examination of the regulatory framework and pedagogical experience related to the use of SMART complexes in vocational education. For visualization of the results, graphical analysis tools were applied, enabling the identification of key trends and problematic aspects of the digitalization of the educational process.

The vocational education system of Ukraine is gradually incorporating the concept of Vocational Education 4.0, which, according to educators, focuses on the integration of digital technologies, an interdisciplinary approach, and personalized learning (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Implementation of Key Features of the Vocational Training 4.0 Concept in Ukraine

Personalized learning has been implemented in 35.4% of educational institutions (5,944 respondents), where students receive materials tailored to their individual needs, contributing to increased motivation and academic success. Digital technologies are utilized in 40.6% of institutions (6,810 respondents), ensuring access to educational materials and enhancing learning efficiency, particularly in distance education formats. Soft skills development is emphasized in 59.1% of institutions (9,922 respondents), focusing on communication, critical thinking, and leadership. An interdisciplinary approach is applied in 41.6% of institutions (6,980 respondents), providing a comprehensive understanding of professional tasks. Collaboration with industry is realized in 24.4% of institutions (4,095 respondents), facilitating students' acquisition of practical experience.

A study involving students and educators highlights the importance of SMART complexes in wartime conditions. The data indicate significant regional variation in the implementation of digital technologies. The western region (23% of students, 31.7% of educators) demonstrates stable infrastructure and a high level of digital competence. The central region (33.3% of students, 28.6% of educators) benefits from access to modern platforms but faces challenges in rural communities. The eastern region (19% of students, 20.2% of educators) encounters the most significant difficulties due to the war, complicating the use of SMART complexes. The southern region (19% of students, 14.3% of educators) suffers from infrastructure instability; however, digital technologies are actively developing in large cities. The northern region (9% of students, 5.2% of educators) has limited digital infrastructure, compelling educators in remote communities to rely on traditional teaching methods. The implementation of SMART complexes depends on access to technology, teacher qualifications, and infrastructure. The western and central regions demonstrate the best performance, whereas the eastern and southern regions face serious challenges. A regionalized approach, considering the specific conditions of each region, is necessary for effective development.

Distance learning is widely used (34.8%), while in-person learning accounts for 33.2%. The northern region predominantly employs a blended learning format (53.6% of students, 80.1% of educators). Distance learning constitutes 32%, whereas in-person

learning accounts for only 14.4% due to the limitations of traditional formats. These findings underscore the importance of adapting educational models to regional conditions to ensure effective learning outcomes.

An analysis of regional differences in educational formats, based on surveys of students and educators, revealed distinct regional characteristics in organizing the educational process. The western region primarily utilizes in-person learning (70%), attributed to stable infrastructure. Blended learning accounts for 23%, while distance learning is minimal. The central region maintains a balance between in-person (54.5%) and blended learning (40%). Distance learning represents a minor share, indicating the accessibility of traditional education. The eastern region relies predominantly on distance learning (63.8% of students, 53.8% of educators) due to military actions and damaged infrastructure. Blended learning constitutes over 30%, while in-person learning is the least common. The southern region is characterized by active use of blended learning (32% of students, 54.2% of educators) due to energy supply instability. Distance learning is widespread (34.8%), whereas in-person learning accounts for 33.2%. The northern region predominantly employs a blended format (53.6% of students, 80.1% of educators). Distance learning constitutes 32%, while in-person learning is limited to 14.4% due to constraints in traditional formats. These findings emphasize the need to adapt educational models to regional conditions to ensure the effectiveness of the learning process.

Survey results on the effectiveness of SMART complexes for education in wartime conditions among educators revealed diverse perspectives, reflecting both positive attitudes and cautious approaches to these technologies in crisis situations (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Assessment of the Effectiveness of SMART Complexes

SMART complexes under martial law demonstrate high potential for ensuring the educational process. A smaller proportion of respondents consider them highly effective, highlighting the possibility of continuing education even in the absence of physical presence. The majority of educators evaluated these technologies as effective, indicating their overall positive role in conditions of limited access to traditional educational resources. Partial effectiveness is noted due to certain limitations, including technical issues, internet instability, or lack of equipment. A small proportion of educators negatively assess SMART complexes, primarily due to infrastructural challenges. The overall results indicate that most respondents recognize SMART complexes as essential for sustaining the educational process under conditions of instability.

The obtained data also allow for an assessment of the impact of SMART complexes on the pace of knowledge and skill acquisition by learners (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. The Impact of SMART Complexes on Learning Pace

Most educators note that these technologies facilitate faster knowledge acquisition due to their interactivity and personalized approach. However, the pace of learning depends on access to resources and the preparedness of educators. This underscores the importance of SMART complexes, particularly in resource-constrained environments, although support programs must be developed to enhance their effectiveness. A student survey revealed significant differences in attitudes toward the personalized approach. A total of 28.4% of respondents reported always receiving individualized instruction, indicating its effectiveness for approximately one-third of students. Additionally, 26.8% felt that a personalized approach was applied occasionally, while 23.2% noted partial implementation. Together, this means that around 80% of students recognized that their learning needs were considered. However, 11.8% of respondents indicated that a personalized approach was not applied to them, suggesting limited adoption of such methodologies in most educational institutions. Furthermore, 9.8% of students were unable to provide an answer, which may indicate insufficient awareness or a lack of clarity in the implementation of this process in certain institutions.

The effective implementation of SMART complexes is hindered by several obstacles. One of the primary challenges is infrastructural limitations. Many vocational education institutions lack reliable Internet access and modern devices that support SMART technologies, particularly in regions close to conflict zones. Addressing this issue requires prioritized investments in infrastructure development. Additionally, many educators lack the necessary skills to effectively use SMART complexes. Comprehensive professional development programs focusing on technical proficiency and pedagogical strategies are crucial. Another barrier is the high cost of acquiring and maintaining SMART complexes. Partnerships with technology providers and the implementation of open-source solutions could help reduce costs and improve accessibility.

Successful integration of SMART complexes necessitates comprehensive support for educators, including the provision of knowledge, resources, and motivation. Professional development programs should encompass training in digital tools, familiarization with the functionalities of SMART complexes, and practical instruction. Intensive courses and regular webinars can help educators incorporate digital technologies into their disciplines. Special attention should be given to training modules that account for the specifics of various subjects, incorporating practical case studies and methodological recommendations. Interactive textbooks featuring video lessons and assessments can enhance material

structuring. To support effective implementation, online communities should be established where educators can share experiences. Mentorship programs and conferences can facilitate a faster adaptation to new technologies. In this context, technical and organizational support is essential: educators must have access to modern equipment, software, and stable internet connectivity. Educational institutions should ensure technical assistance and incentivize educators through bonuses, public recognition, or career advancement opportunities.

4 Conclusions

The analysis of survey data encompassing 16,792 students and 4,600 educators from vocational education institutions confirms the high relevance of integrating SMART complexes into the educational process. The implementation of SMART complexes in students' vocational training has proven to be highly effective, particularly in the face of challenges posed by martial law. SMART complexes, which incorporate elements of artificial intelligence and analytical tools, enable the rapid adaptation of educational materials to students' individual learning needs and capabilities, enhance learning efficiency, and allow for flexible adjustment of instructional content in accordance with current labor market demands and educational conditions.

In the central-eastern region, where participants in the educational process frequently experience air raid alerts and power outages, a distance learning model remains the only viable option for vocational education, ensuring that students can learn at a personalized pace. Conversely, in western regions, where face-to-face learning continues to dominate, a fixed learning pace prevails, disregarding students' individual educational needs and capabilities.

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